

KORPORATIV HUQUQDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK (PPP) TUSHUNCHASINI ANIQLASHDA NAZARIY MUAMMOLAR

Ibragimova Muxinur San'at qizi

Toshkent davlat yuridik universiteti

Email: mokhinuribragimova2002@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775352>

ANNOTATSIYA	KALIT SO‘ZLAR
Mazkur maqolada “davlat-xususiy sheriklik” (DXSh) tushunchasining aniqlanishiga oid nazariy muammolar yoritiladi. DXShning huquqiy tabiati, tarmoqlararo mohiyati va davlat-huquqiy tizimdagi o‘rni tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada O‘zbekiston, AQSh va Yevropa Ittifoqida qo‘llanilayotgan DXSh ta’riflariga solishtirma tahlil berilib.	davlat-xususiy sheriklik, huquqiy tabiati, shartnoma, institut, xavf, xususiy sektor, huquq nazariyasi, O‘zbekiston.

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ВОПРОСЫ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ПОНЯТИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННО-ЧАСТНОГО ПАРТНЁРСТВА В КОРПОРАТИВНОМ ПРАВЕ (ГЧП)

Ибрагимова Мохинур Санъат кизи

Ташкентский государственный юридический университет

эл. почта: mokhinuribragimova2002@gmail.com

АННОТАЦИЯ	КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА
В статье рассматриваются теоретические проблемы определения понятия «государственно-частное партнёрство» (ГЧП), включая анализ междисциплинарного характера данной правовой конструкции, её правовой природы и места в системе публично-правовых отношений. Проведён сравнительный обзор подходов к определению ГЧП в Узбекистане, США и Европейском союзе.	государственно-частное партнёрство, правовая природа, контракт, институт, риски, частный сектор, теория права, Узбекистан.

THEORETICAL ISSUES IN DEFINING THE CONCEPT OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN CORPORATE LAW (PPP)

Ibragimova Mokhinur San'at qizi

Tashkent state university of law

Email: mokhinuribragimova2002@gmail.com

ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
This article studies the theoretical problems in understanding	public-private

what public–private partnership (PPP) means by pointing out its complex legal background, how it is classified, and its position in the context of public law. Examples from Uzbekistan, the United States, and the European Union are used to give a clear comparison of what PPPs mean.

partnership, legal nature, contract, institution, risk, private sector, legal theory, Uzbekistan.

Despite the widespread use of public–private partnership (PPP) mechanisms in both international and national practice, the legal theory still lacks a unified and well-established definition of this phenomenon. This is primarily due to the interdisciplinary nature of PPP, which encompasses elements of administrative, civil, financial, and corporate law, as well as the variety of forms and models applied in different legal systems.

In exploring the theoretical challenges of defining PPP, it is essential to clarify the object of such legal relations. According to Paragraph 4 of Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Public–Private Partnership”, “The object of a public–private partnership includes property, property complexes, public infrastructure, as well as the design, construction, creation, supply, financing, reconstruction, modernization, operation and maintenance carried out within the framework of a PPP project; land plots; and also works (services) and innovations to be introduced during project implementation”. In other words, the object of PPP encompasses property and infrastructure used or created within a joint project. These may include buildings, facilities, land, as well as related services—from design and construction to modernization, operation, and maintenance. Furthermore, PPP objects include innovative solutions and technologies introduced during the implementation of the partnership project.

The concept of public-private partnership (PPP) in corporate law presents several theoretical challenges due to its interdisciplinary nature, encompassing elements of public, private, and corporate legal frameworks. One of the main issues lies in the lack of a unified definition, as PPP is variously interpreted as a contractual arrangement, a governance mechanism, or a hybrid legal structure. In corporate law, defining PPP becomes even more complex when private participation is formalized through entities such as joint-stock companies, limited liability companies, or special purpose vehicles (SPVs), each governed by distinct legal norms. This raises questions about the legal status of participants, the balance between public oversight and corporate autonomy, and the delineation of rights and responsibilities. As a result, the absence of conceptual clarity can hinder the development of coherent legal frameworks and create barriers to effective PPP implementation in practice.

In the United States, PPP is understood as “a contractual agreement between the government and a private company that enables the latter to participate, in an agreed form, in public ownership and perform functions traditionally considered the responsibility of the public sector. Such an agreement typically entails the reconstruction or construction of a publicly owned asset and/or its operation and management. Ownership rights usually remain with the state, and even after transferring the object to a private company, the government retains legal ownership. PPP covers both straightforward agreements and more complicated ones, in which the private party takes on risks, plans procedures, and deals with penalties, as well as construction, modernization, running, and managing the whole project”.

In the European Union, PPP is understood as public authorities joining hands with businesses to develop, finance, upgrade, manage, or operate infrastructure and services for society. This means that in both regions, PPP emphasis is on the state and private business jointly taking action to achieve important goals for society.

In the U.S., PPPs are mainly based on contracts and keeping the project in the public sector’s hands, but the European Union prefers partnerships between various institutions and using various strategies for PPPs. PPP is characterized by sharing risks, using joint resources, collaborating for a long term, and achieving results, as both agree. Using these approaches can help build and change the PPP institution in Uzbekistan in line with the country’s needs and development plans.

One important issue is understanding how PPP works as a category: to some, it means making a contract, but to others, it refers to having private firms assist in how public tasks are carried out. Therefore, the situation for the participants’ legal status, risk duties, liability, and handling disputes becomes inconsistent.

There are challenges in telling PPP apart from public procurement, leasing government property, or carrying out privatization. Unlike the usual approach to public procurement, PPPs normally consist of extended cooperative efforts and share risks; still, it is sometimes hard to tell these approaches apart, especially in developing countries.

According to A.V. Belitskaya, PPP is an official agreement between public bodies and private businesses, running for a set time, that deals with

government assets that are of direct interest and control. In this way, companies join forces and share investment responsibilities so that projects meaningful to the nation and public can be executed smoothly.

A number of academics are still debating how PPPs fit into the law. It is a common view among researchers that PPP is essentially a civil form of dealing, since it features many elements from civil law, for instance, the legal status of businesses, contracts, blended agreements, property rights, and relations with assets.

From our point of view, PPP is a legal institution that helps public organizations and private businesses cooperate for important and strategic aims by joining their resources, know-how, and money.

In books and articles on education, two major theories are commonly taught. It underlines how PPP operates based on economics and law, and its main purpose is to carry out social-value projects using private money. The other deals with regulations and management matters, pointing out that it is important for both parties to have their interests balanced and have solid control structures.

Introducing PPP projects has caused the need for a universal system of classifying them. Various countries have adopted concession models, DBFO, BOT, lease agreements, and joint ventures, and every country has its own interpretation of what the partnerships allow.

Consequently, since PPP isn't described the same way by all theories, both law practice and regulations may be difficult to create. Since PPP is not well developed yet in Uzbekistan, it needs to be brought into line with the country's rules and regulations.

To sum up, the research on PPP makes it clear that there is no generally accepted explanation for PPP either in international or local laws. Since there are many types of models and forms, and the rules apply to several areas of law, there are many different views on what it is legally.

Since the PPP institution is still growing in Uzbekistan, it is essential for the country to have a well-defined and consistent theory and law on the subject. For this reason, proper implementation allows legal regulations to improve, helps in fertile application, and makes it possible to embrace valuable international lessons in the country. One can clearly see that PPP has to start with a strong grasp of its purpose: centering on long-term partnership between public and private sectors, based on sharing risk, bringing benefits to all, and pursuing results that are important to society.

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public-Private Partnership" dated May 10, 2019, No. ZRU-537, as amended on October 4, 2023.
2. Report to Congress on Public-Private Partnerships. U.S. Department of Transportation, 2004.
3. Green Paper on Public-Private Partnerships and Community Law on Public Contracts and Concessions. Brussels, April 30, 2004.
4. Belitskaya, A.V. Legal Definition of Public-Private Partnership // Legislation. 2009. No. 8. p. 42.
5. Krivopalova, A.A. On the Problem of Defining the Concept of Public-Private Partnership // Journal "Problems of Economics and Legal Practice". 2013. Article 62.